

EMPTY SPACE: THE SIGNATURE OF ALMIGHTY

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Abstract:

Considering the energy groups $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$, $SU(24)$,..... releases large number of different free energies of small wave-lengths but high frequencies assumed to be mathematically covered a complex space-time created nonlocal consciousness with nonphysical particles by wave-function collapses by creating through quantum dots after quantum-superposition. Maintaining the similar processes created local consciousness producing with different bounded structures through physical particles accordingly with the increase of energy wave lengths after phase change then by resonances of waves created several close-boundary body systems according to the contact or collected by light to heavy matter particles. We thus considered two important stages of consciousness-creation as before[up-to the theory of $SU(23)$] & after[from the symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$ & GUT of $SU(5)$] the creation of magnetic monopoles by the energy group $U(1)$, the electrodynamics group after phase change, gradually then increasing the energy wave-lengths then collapses created different kind of body-system, in that reason we may consider mathematically the space-time of the whole universe as $R + iR$ of $(4 + D)$ -dimensions instead of Einstein's 4-dimensional space-time R , within which it constructed everything including our physical universe. Again, we need to be considered two phases simultaneously for explanation of everything, i.e. the existences of short-wave lengths background energies are taken into account for avoiding error of measurements when using physical equipments or tools, such as problem of entanglement, EPR experiment, uncertainty principle, wave-particle duality etc. all kind of experiments were done with respect to the physical matter particles or comparable long wave-lengths rays where we ignore the background of short wave lengths nonphysical particles which are essential for accounting of any kind of measurements, for example, we know that no real-time can't possible for the measurement between entangle particles, but it is wrong, because there is a very short time between the particles or infinitesimal small time are required for measurement of positions between the two entangle particles, although, any quantum particles are always remained in wave form but it appears as particles after increases the curvatures or wave lengths changes with contacting matter containing rays which are using for experimental measurements, hence then it appeared as a particle character only after collapsing. According to the Einstein's GRT, that real time can't defined outside the gravitating sphere i.e. when time measured between two particles remained in other phase, time is to be considered then mathematically as imaginary. But if we wants to avoid the imaginary space-time, we need to be considered the space-time of the physical universe is R^2 instead of Einstein's 'R', the scale factor then outside the gravitating sphere that means internal space-time belongs to other phase will be as $R_1^2 = -R^2$, which shows, no complex space-time arises for any explanation of early quantum universe.

Keywords: Vacuum Energy, Consciousness, Superposition of Waves, Wave Function Collapses, Quantum Dots, Brain Pattern of Bounded Systems, Phase Changing System, Dark Energy, Latent Energy, Exotic Matter Fluid or Dark Matter, Ordinary Matter.

Introduction:

We assumed that our Physical Universe including all kind of matter oriented conscious & non-conscious bounded-close-body-system are as animates & inanimate within it appeared through nonphysical particles of Non-Physical Universe (so called vacuum filled with dense short waves but high frequencies energies as signature of almighty producing quantum dots with their superposition by wave functions collapses) by a dynamical process through continuous symmetry breaking called Generalised Gaussian Energy Group (GGEG), can be expressed mathematically are as follows:

From GUT theory of Standard Model of Physics, we have $SU(5) \supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$; then SUT theory of $SU(11) \supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$ and $SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$;

$SU(47) \supset SU(24) \times SU(23) \times U(1); \dots$ so on. We have therefore, $SU(12n-1) \supset SU(6n) \times SU(6n-1) \times U(1)$, where, $n = 2^0, 2^1, 2^2, 2^3, 2^4, \dots, \infty$ i.e. $SU(12n-1) \supset SU(6n) \times \dots \times SU(24) \times SU(12) \times SU(6) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$.

In my present dissertation, we assumed to be the theories of three-stages, which are very much essential for the present epoch, the theories of Unified Group $SU(23)$ in other phase of nonphysical mode, then after phase transition system appears unified groups $SU(11)$ & $SU(5)$ in the present mode of physical universe, both are plays the crucial roles for unfolding everything within the physical universe, out of which the theory of $SU(23)$ are responsible for discussion of how to appear from nonphysical universe to the present mode of physical universe (like it changes from gaseous to vapor stages below the critical temperature) passing through a critical stage assuming as the entry state of birth process. Then unfolding accordingly to the changes of dark energies replacing by dark matter with introducing information carries local consciousness from other phase to the present phase. Maybe found with random creation of bounded-close-conscious mechanical body-system by exchanging exotic matter fluids into ordinary matters after unfolding with so called space-time of physical universe or multi-universe, which then expanding according to the theory of $SU(11)$, that's are also responsible for the creation of random bounded conscious soul oriented living body-system like as Human, trees etc. After constructing physical universe by superposition of short energy wave lengths or it's resonating waves after collapsing in a suitable situation, then body-system constructed by space-time reduction and then orchestrated objective reduction in human brain microtubules through wave function collapses produces by quantum dots with immediate symmetry breaking of GUT $SU(5)$. Hence there created several bounded dynamical ordinary soul oriented matter body-system with or without making a particular brain place or a brain pattern system etc. i.e. like a single celled protozoa type, maybe there is an internal generalized places other than particular brain place, but generally containing a blueprint programming within the system for future development, such maybe in the nonliving body-system constructed like as Galaxies with blueprint including the internal body-parts as stars-family etc. Then journey started for various conscious and non-conscious dynamical matter-body-systems within the physical matter oriented universe. The random creation of animates & inanimate which are also interacted to each other through information carries background small-waves including with various long-waves appears as local consciousness.

According to the above-mentioned mathematical explanation of the new energy sources of Wider Universe was thus filled with different kind of high & low frequencies but small & long wave lengths of energy-waves including its resonating vibrations of wave functions, then quarks, leptons, quark-likes & lepton-likes etc. which are then tightly binding by the bosons to their respective individual subgroups creating random vibrating-particles seems to be physical universe unfolding from lump of matters, then found various soul oriented conscious-closed-living-body-system unfolding through soft matters which are therefore interacting externally as well as internally for up-gradation of its body-parts towards the aim of a complete individuality of the body-system producing through different kind of matter elements as required for completeness of body-system as per instruction contained in blueprint. Then constructed local consciousness by the energy group $SU(6)$ in the framework of $SU(6) \times U(1)$, may gradually interacting to the close-body-system with other body-system including by using outside nonlocal consciousness. Accordingly to the gathering of information developing the mental & physical body-parts of the close-system, which was carry forward by or converted after constructing brain-patterns through quantum dots within the place of microtubules of human brain-like neurons through orchestrated objective reduction, details explained by famous scientists Roger Penrose & Stuart-Hameroff otherwise the same was done by space-time reduction for construction of body-system such as galaxies, stars etc. without any particular brain-place i.e. maybe

conducting through generalized places of body-parts within the body-system like as maintaining living status of single celled body-system protozoa, a single-cell lives having no brain place but if you observed its life-style found as all-round improvements, it also carries information through local consciousness etc. We try to understand that human brain produced local consciousness, but it may be wrong, there may be constructed a particular place or places, from where as assumed to be emerged consciousness but those place maintain a crucial role and associated with the creation of thoughts by interaction with mind-soul of the matter oriented body system called as local consciousness. An analogy will illustrate the scenario we observed as moon-light produced by moon, but it is wrong, only there is a reflection of sun-light. Again, without any particular place as like human brain-place, the same event may occurred another places by wave-function collapses, i.e. by collapsing the waves containing nonphysical & physical particles, maybe collapsing such as an organic-cells or any of body-parts of the individual close bounded-body-system because all quantum particles are always vibrating. Therefore, we may be considered that such human brain-place are like as a sub-centre of local-consciousness because it will activated by combining the mind-soul through internal interaction with sense-organs producing as mind-body relation with soul by the energy group $SU(2)$ working in the framework of $SU(2) \times U(1)$ influencing by outside interaction of $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$,.....etc. with respect to their frameworks of $SU(6) \times U(1)$ & $SU(12) \times U(1)$,.....etc. respectively through electromagnetic energy group $U(1)$, which produced magnetic mono-pole, once created can't destroyed. Hence, we may considered, the human-brain-like of other lives, may have used their brain-place as a relay-centre-like, because through this brain-place, all incoming & outgoing information can interacted with other parts of body-system and an information carry-forwarded as internal instructions considering as thought producing by interacting with sense organs called mind, connected by outside & inner sided of body-parts through an internal or external network-system by interacting through different framework-system of electromagnetic force-field.

Human Brain is Like a Information Relay-Centre:

In wider sense the universe is an ocean of new energies of high frequencies but short wave lengths producing small curvatures which are therefore changes steadily but slowly to the long curvatures like as deep water ocean of high frequencies short-wave lengths water-tide changes to the long waves of comparably low frequencies as it advanced towards the sea-shore including we found different nature of behavior like as sea-water current, tidal effects etc. observing differences in different places of sea-water i.e. here by new energies after creation of space-time-matter with bounded-system comparably by short wave-lengths changes to long wave-lengths as it advanced towards the contact of matter-base along with production of new elements. That means small curvatures formed by short-wave-lengths of the universe slowly changes to the long curvatures after symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$ including with immediate other symmetry breaking of GUT $SU(5)$. We therefore understood that symmetry breaking of different unified groups with different phases were started from Big-Rip singularity are therefore random process till it reaching below a critical stage of symmetry breaking of the unified group $SU(23)$, arising in a phase change situation then symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$ & $SU(5)$. All body-parts of the bounded-system-physical-universe are therefore created by non-living elements as well as by livings are tightly binding by the quark-likes & quarks etc. with different kind of bosons then unfolding different kind of ordinary matter elements with increasing its atomic numbers accordingly to the wave function collapses. Therefore, eternal consciousness creating nonphysical energies with particles are changes to physical energies with particles by superposition of energy waves or by the resonating vibration waves within the bounded-system appears then as condensed new matter

energy wave-curvatures through condensation process creating as quantum dots by wave function collapses. The similar was occurring in neuron-microtubules for the formations of human brain-cell including other living-cells. Again, seems that brain cell produced consciousness after creating brain-pattern through internal collapsing of the aromatic-compound-bonds etc. through protein structures changes in human brain-microtubules, but in my consideration the brain cell is likely to be a sub-centre or relay centre of consciousness instead of production place. There may be created an electro-magnetic organic-store-room by using micro-cells as memory, like as magnetic-audio-visual-tape-recorders, considering it is an information storing centre, otherwise relay-centre of information-carrying-place from which likely to be forwarded information to all parts of the body-system assumed as consciousness working for self-realization of individuality through interacting with mind then creating thoughts or vice-versa by interaction with sense organs. This random process are always active either in sleeping or non sleeping stages i.e. when mind forcibly anesthetic some particular brain-cells with respect to the awakening state, that means forcibly inactive otherwise concentrated anyhow to increase the work capacity through mind-force by using a network system in the framework of $SU(2) \times U(1)$ by the energy group $SU(2)$ through by internal interaction, simultaneously strong interaction may have using by other energy groups such as $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$,....., through the frameworks of $SU(6) \times U(1)$ & $SU(12) \times U(1)$,....etc. after connecting with global or universal network-system which are as responsible for creating telepathy etc. Hence, you can observe or understood the past or future-something in advance without any physical connection or physically present there, maybe through dreams or anyhow by concentrated the mind with awakening situation (like as you are in time-travel, explained by famous scientist Albert Einstein) and it also observed events are sometime true-based as advanced information, maybe as non imaginative i.e. real or physical. So far it is possible only when your mind strongly interacting with outside information carries consciousness by using through universal network-systems i.e. through local & nonlocal consciousness maybe actively participate in that situation by using the aforesaid energies, relatively which maybe good or bad is a different question, that event may also stored in memory. Again, the energy group $SU(2)$ are associated with carrying local information through the interaction of mind-body relation are engaged for physical fitness of the body-system while energy groups $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$,....are associated with development of mental-ability, combining both are developing the bounded conscious body-system sending information to its body-parts for recovering any damages of physical health as well as the mental-health or both, of the individual close-body-system through an internal network-system as like nerves-system by collecting information from physical universe through external network system otherwise or failure of this, we need to medical help in an acute situation. After then considering living body-system developing by Darwinism for all living organisms evolve over time through natural selection.

Appearance of Conscious Physical Universe:

We introduced in my theories a series of new energy sources as $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$, $SU(24)$,..... ∞ beyond standard model of physics. My present dissertation is to be considering an earlier stages of quantum physics from the unified theory of $SU(23)$ in other phase created two distinct character's of energy groups $SU(12)$ & $SU(11)$ [$SU(23) \supset SU(12) \times SU(11) \times U(1)$] of 22-dimensional space-times, then found the theory of super unified group $SU(11)$ which also gave two distinct character's energy group $SU(6)$ & $SU(5)$ by the symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$ [$\supset SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1)$] of 10-dimensional space-time beyond the standard model of physics and finally we found Einstein's 4-dimensional Physical Universe by the symmetry breaking of GUT $SU(5) \supset SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$, the Standard Model of Physics.

Our physical universe is thus appeared from symmetry breaking of SU(23), like as from gaseous phase to vapor, after then symmetry breaking of SUT SU(11), then appears a stage of exotic matter-fluid state as dark-matter fluid appearing through like as colloidal stages. Finally we found the symmetry breaking of GUT SU(5), the ordinary matter stage. Then unfolding expected matter oriented physical universe as real universe explained by GRT including all other bounded-body-system.

We therefore considering a soul consisting conscious-bounded-dynamical-body-system appears from non-physical stages through symmetry breaking of SU(23), a phase change situation through producing a nascent stage of dynamically bounded soul oriented conscious-matter-body-system as physical universe of the stages of 10-dimensional space-times, so called real physical universe arises with the symmetry breaking of the Super Unified Gaussian Energy Group SU(11) influencing by interaction through energy group SU(12) with then immediate symmetry breaking of GUT of SU(5). In the theory of unified group SU(23) it is possible to change 132 number of bosons of SU(12) into 132 number of bosons of SU(11) by exchanging the bosons of SU(23), this large numbers of bosons are required for changing the phase including then quark-likes but lepton-types energy particles are found, there may be 6 groups each having of 22-numbers of quark-likes nonphysical high energy particles of high frequencies are requiring or releasing for completing the phase changing systems then reaching below the critical stage were ready for another symmetry breaking SUT of SU(11) because we still remembered that our physical universe unfolded with 10-dimensional space-time where (10-7)-dimensional flat universe stage, no adiabatic stages of temperature are arises.

Gradually then emerged a beautiful physical universe or multiple-universe including different conscious & non-conscious matter-body-system within it unfolding through symmetry breaking of SU(11) & SU(5), as like as there is a big candle-flame of physical universe with families of unaccounted small candle-flame like matter-body-system as animates & inanimate. Which are then silently working through the direction of incoming information carries nonlocal consciousness constructed by SU(12), SU(24),..... ∞ in the framework of SU(12) $\times$ U(1); SU(24) $\times$ U(1),..... ∞ , as well as unfolding the local consciousness by the energy group SU(6) into the framework of SU(6) $\times$ U(1) interacting through U(1) which creating magnetic mono-pole by the symmetry breaking of SUT SU(11). There constructed soul oriented mechanical living-body-system along with blueprint towards the fulfillment of future development, then automatically it adopting or adjusted by catching incoming information through holographic system by human brain-like places or other places. The creation & working process of consciousness maybe comparing with broadcasting-systems (see my articles such as How "SU" Levels Are Imply for Life & Consciousness) where it was done by the pseudo-actors creating information dots at pseudo-studio of infinite space-time with non-physical particle waves as well as by physical particle-waves of finite space-time of universe. Then information-carries nonlocal consciousness working accordingly with different kind of primary information stored blueprint for different individual system with respect to a particular physical universe or many more different particular physical-universe. Accordingly we then found random creation of matter oriented bounded mind-soul consisting self conscious body-system. Considering all quantum particles are vibrating, then nonlocal & local information again carry-forwarded from mother body-system to the newly born well defined conscious mind-soul consisting matter oriented body-system along with some common instinct from the existing mother body-system like as pre-installed information are as free installed with computer hardware-body-system then advanced accordingly to following separate individually constructed blueprint for future smooth improvement of body-system. Thus assuming energy group SU(6) creates local consciousness with local information in the frame-work of SU(6) $\times$ U(1) as well as it

changes ordinary matters from exotic matter fluids by changing 30-number of bosons of SU(6) changes to the bosons of SU(5) by exchanging the bosons of SU(11).

Now the physical universe expanded combining with expansion of its body-parts as like as expansion of body-system of galaxies, clusters, super clusters, star family, such as solar family including with all other individual living-bodies like humans etc. all are as body-parts of physical universe. The physical universe always maintaining the balance through dynamical system for smooth development and for smooth running of individual soul oriented conscious-closed-body-system. Then continue the blueprint-based improvement till it reaching to the extreme maturity-situation like as Big-Break singularity of physical universe. After then contraction started (showing in my article 'The Complex Quantum and Classical Pseudo-Tachyonic Universe') till to the non-functioning of all its body-parts i.e. called death, finally after Big-Crunch singularity, all body-parts of death bodies are disappears within the deep ocean-like energies of infinite space-time in other phase.

RAPID EXPANSION OF PHYSICAL UNIVERSE:

The experimental observation for finding expansion rate of physical universe was done by the occurrences of red shift of light between stars without accounting the expansion rate of star contained galaxy, although, such are not only true conclusion for calculation of expansion rate of the physical universe but also we need to account the expansion rate of dynamical close-body-system, as expansion of star contained galaxy. That's why theoretical calculation of the rate of expansion of physical universe are different from observing calculation of red shift of the stars, due to the non-addition of combining expansion rate such as combining the individual expansion of galaxy body-system including with expanding body-system of the physical universe i.e. by resultant expanding rates of both are need to be accounted for actual calculation.

My consideration is thus approaches to alternative cosmology as Kantowski–Sachs universe model of new unfolding universe, are different from Einstein's GRT, rather it is an extension of GRT but very much essential for the present epoch, where metric tensors are assumed to be as $\mathbf{T}_0^0 = \rho$ (matter energy density), $\mathbf{T}_1^1 = \epsilon_1$ (latent energy density) and negative pressure $\mathbf{T}_2^2 = \mathbf{T}_3^3 = -\mathbf{p}$

We then found an important relation $\epsilon_1 = \rho - 2\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{K}$, where 'K' is the Consciousness creating factor contained c' the velocity of photon-like particles in vapor-like stages where $c' > c$, the velocity of photon-like in the tachyon field and c is the velocity of light.

According to the famous law of Einstein, $E = Mc^2$, the folded internal space of the universe unfolded with energy changes to matter with the creation of space-time. The expanding universe was then considering by Einstein as homogeneous closed spherical i.e. we may then consider, $E \propto R^3$, where the scale factor R was assumed to be the radius of the closed spherical universe. But after practical observation of red shift we found the expansion rate of the physical universe are far more differ from Einstein's theoretical expectation because the universe actually expanding exponentially as shown in my articles 'The Complex Model Of The Quantum Universe'.

We then consider a $(4 + D)$ -dimensional Friedmann–Robertson–Walker type universe having complex scale factor $R + iR_1$, where R is the scale factor corresponding to the usual 4-dimensional Universe while (iR_1) is that of D -dimensional space an extra dimensions are associated with consciousness. It is then compared with $(4 + D)$ -dimensional Kaluza–Klein cosmology having two scale factors R and $a (= iR_1)$, the internal space-time. The Wheeler–DeWitt equation is constructed and general solution was obtained. It was found that for $D = 6$ (i.e. in $4 + 6 = 10$ dimension), the Wheeler–DeWitt equation is symmetric under the exchange of $R_1 \leftrightarrow R$ and $(10-7)$ dimensions, the universe was then flat, therefore appearance of adiabatic stage is quite impossible in this stage, after then from 6-dimensions the physical universe may be closed with arising adiabatic stage. We may

compared with Einstein's GRT like as D-dimensional internal space-time 'a' ($= iR_1$) of the Kaluza-Klein cosmology with scale factor R_1 including unfolding Einstein's space-time of the scale factor R , in such a way that $R_1^2 = -R^2$, i.e. R^2 stand the real unfolded space-time instead of R in the existing present phase with respect to the Einstein's GRT while R_1^2 is that of the internal space-time as of (iR) in the other phase. Then from $E = Mc^2$ or $E \propto R^3$ can be changes into $E \propto (R^2)^3$ or $E \propto R^6$, where we assumed that real space-time as R^2 instead of R , filled with dark energies carrying local & nonlocal information, dark matters including ordinary matter energies constructed matter body systems and internal space-time (iR) filled with dark energies including nonlocal information will be as $-R^2$ (negative sign indicating of other phase) i.e. $R_1^2 = -R^2$ in another phase, hence after phase changes the equation $E = Mc^2$ changes by $E \propto R^6$, which maybe very near to the practically observation of calculation of expansion rate.

MEASUREMENT ERRORS:

In our physical universe, all kind of measurement or experiment was done mostly under the theory of SM & GRT i.e. using any kind of instrument or tools as such using rays for experiments which are constructed by matter oriented particles. That means experiment was conducted by the rays of matter particles. When nonphysical particles of wave characters were came into contact with the matter oriented particles then short wave-length increased by long wave-lengths, as a result wave character collapses or converted by particle characters. Hence in any kind of experimental results, we found a possible errors, for example between two entangle quantum particles are basically connected by a single wave carries nonphysical information beyond the standard model of physics i.e. experiment was done by rays of outside extra energies of physical particle. If such a distance between two particles of entanglement maybe considered in other phase as $S = n \lambda(it)$ or $S + iS_1 = 0 + in\lambda t$, with respect to GRT, where 'n' is the high frequency, ' λ ' is the wave length between entangle particles connected by a single energy wave where real time can't defined by GRT or infinitesimal small time are between the entangle particles in other phase, assuming classically as there imaginary time, that means existence of real physical distance can't possible measuring between two entangle particles because two distant entangle particles were linked by a single wave as information carrying small wave having particles called as wave-function are therefore nonphysical which appeared in a single position by wave-function collapses when contacting with matter-based particle-rays.

So that we need to emphasized on new force or fifth force created by the new energy group $SU(6)$ including the framework of $SU(6) \times U(1)$ for explanation of anything because it creates a new type of electromagnetic force-field.

Conclusion:

We need to require more importance on new energy sources of $SU(6)$, $SU(12)$, $SU(24)$,.....are as signatures of almighty. Require widely consideration of the appearance of physical universe by unfolding from 10-dimensional space-time instead of Einstein's 4-dimensional universe that means we required to a revision of SM and need to be an extension of GRT. Given more & more importance on observation by experimental result regarding the existences of new force creator energy source $SU(6)$ and indentified the characters & behaviors including its important roles for the creation of everything within the real physical universe. We try to proof that new force creator energy group $SU(6)$ plays an important roles for carries information as assuming local consciousness. More research are required to proof that it plays an important roles for the creation of matter body-system and also influencing for the symmetry breaking of the GUT group $SU(5)$. Every

quantum explanation we need to consider the background dense nonphysical high frequencies short waves lengths energies.

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